

Survey of Macrofungal Diversity in Sutargaon village, Kamrup district, Assam

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Abstract

The Kamrup district of Assam lies in a zone of high ecological and climatic heterogeneity, bordering the Brahmaputra riverine system, hill slopes, and patches of semi-evergreen to moist deciduous forests. This geographical setting supports a rich assemblage of plant life, both in number of taxa and in functional/ecological variety. The present study is a combination of field survey and photographic documentation of the macrofungal species spotted at the Sutargaon village of Kamrup district, Assam. The study was conducted from February to May, 2025. Opportunistic sampling method was used for the study. A total of 28 specimens were recorded in the survey, out of which 14 specimens are reported to be edible, and the other 14 are inedible. Two of the specimen are known to be deadly poisonous.

Keywords: *Macrofungi, diversity, North Guwahati, Kamrup, Assam.*

Introduction

Macrofungi are a diverse group of fungi characterized by large, conspicuous fruiting bodies that can be easily observed with the naked eye. They form an essential part of terrestrial ecosystems, and play critical roles in nutrient cycling, decomposition, and symbiotic relationships with other organisms. The term “macrofungi” generally refers to members of the groups Basidiomycota and Ascomycota that bear visible sporocarps (fruiting bodies), like mushrooms, puffballs, boletes, morels, and bracket fungi. Macrofungi are fungi that produce macroscopic spore-bearing structures visible without the aid of a microscope [1]. These fruiting bodies, or sporocarps, appear from a network of mycelium (hyphae) that grows within the substratum that could be soil, wood, or litter. Many of these fungi are saprotrophs or decomposers which contribute significantly to nutrient cycling as primary producers, and also play a significant role in ecological food web [2]. They grow best in rainy season and can flourish in all kinds of substrates such as rotten wood, decaying organic matter, grassy ground,

etc. [3]. Macrofungi are a crucial part of the forest ecosystem. They provide a wide variety of ecosystem services such as medicinal, ecological, and biotechnical applications [4], [5]. They are known to participate in nutrient cycling and act as decomposers and mutualistic symbionts, which are essential in humans' needs [6].

The area selected for this study was Sutargaon, a village in the Kamrup district of Assam. Sutargaon (26.45°-26.48° N, 91.73°-91.77° E) lies on the northern bank of the Brahmaputra river. The area is characterized by a subtropical humid climate with hot summers and heavy rainfall. The average annual temperatures range from 12-38°C. Winter temperatures range from 15-25°C during the day and 8-15°C at night. Summer temperatures range from 25 to 38°C during the day and 15 to 25°C at night. The area witnesses an average annual rainfall of around 1752 mm to 2125.4 mm annually. The vegetation in the area includes a variety of flowering plants, vegetables, herbs, shrubs, fruit-bearing trees, and native plants. This area is also known for its rich biodiversity. Systematic and periodic survey of different forests, gardens and other habitats were undertaken during February 2025 to May 2025.

Fig. 1: Location/ GPS Map of Sutargaon village, Kamrup district, Assam

Methods and Materials

The sampling method involved walking throughout the entire study region and collecting macrofungi covering up to 80% of the area. Sampling of the ground-dwelling macrofungi involved careful extraction of the fruiting body from the soil and leaf litter, ensuring that the basal surface was intact. Tree-dwelling macrofungi were sampled by cutting off the basidiomata from the trees without disturbing the spore surfaces present below. The survey and collection of macrofungi were conducted in 5 different village locations of Sutargaon, under different agro-climatic conditions, during the month of February to May, 2025. The map of the survey sites along with their GPS coordinates is provided in Figure 1. The collections were performed in different seasons, like the end of winter (February), spring (March - April) and summer (May). The opportunistic sampling method of collection of macrofungi described in [2] was used for collection of macrofungi. This method involves carefully walking through a study site and collecting conspicuous sporocarps. Soft macrofungi were carefully collected by using forceps/ free hand, while the macrofungi growing on wood were collected along with small part of wood. All collected samples were carefully wrapped in aluminum foil, placed in an air-tight zip-lock bag and labelled with the collection number, location, date, and other data. Photographs of the mushroom were taken in their natural habitat. Field labels were attached to every specimen which included a date, location, habitat, a brief note on distinguishing macroscopic features, collection number, microhabitat and the collectors code [7] and deposited in the Department of Botany, North Gauhati College. The macrofungi were identified by studying the micro morphological features [8], [9] and also by studying the macro morphological features.

Results

During the study conducted from February to May 2025, a total of 28 species of macrofungi were recorded. The collected data reflects a wide range of macrofungal diversity growing on different substrates such as soil, dead wood, termite mounds, and leaf litter. Field observations revealed variation in colour, shape, size, and habitat preference among the recorded specimens. Some of the detailed observation of the macrofungal species collected, have been presented in Table 1, as presented below:

Table 1: Names of macrofungi collected from the study area and their characteristics:

Sl. No.	Scientific Name	Common Name	Macro/ Micro-Morphological Features	Habitat/ Collection month	Edibility/ Common Uses
1.	<i>Agaricus bisporus</i> (J.E. Lange) Imbach Agaricaceae	Button mushroom/ White mushroom	Fleshy, convex, white/ light brown cap, narrow free gills, sturdy white stem with a persistent ring.	Grows in rich organic soils, compost, grasslands/ February	Edible
2.	<i>Amanita phalloides</i> (Vaill. ex Fr.) Link Amanitaceae	Death cap	Yellowish-green to olive-brown, smooth cap, white gills free from the stem, a white, skirt-like annulus; distinct sack-like volva at the base.	Found near deciduous trees/ May	Deadly poisonous
3.	<i>Armillaria mellea</i> (Vahl) P. Kumm. Physalacriaceae	Honey Fungus	Clustered, honey-yellow to brown-capped mushrooms with a prominent white/yellow membranous ring on the stem and white spores.	Decaying wood and roots of hardwood and conifer trees, often in forests/ May	Edible
4.	<i>Coprinellus disseminates</i> (Pers.) J.E. Lange Psathyrellaceae	Fairy inkcap / Trooping crumble cap	Stem slender, fragile, hollow, and white, often with a slightly pubescent or minutely hairy surface; small campanulate, convex to hemispherical; initially whitish, cream-colored, turning greyish-yellow to brownish as it matures; surface characteristically plicate or sulcate-striate from the centre to the margin.	Grows in dense clusters on decaying wood and stumps/ May	Edible (but not flavourful or substantial)

5.	<i>Crepidotus mollis</i> (Schaeff.) Crepidotaceae	Soft slipper or Peeling oysterling	Kidney-shaped, white-to-ochre cap, distinctive elastic, gelatinous cuticle.	Decaying wood in damp forests/ February	Inedible.
6.	<i>Daldinia concentrica</i> (Bolton) Ces. & De Not. Xylariaceae	Cramp Balls	Spherical, cushion-shaped; hard, dark-brown to black, glossy surface.	Dead or decaying hardwood, especially ash trees/ March	Inedible
7.	<i>Deconica coprophila</i> (Bull.) P. Karst. Strophariaceae	Dung-loving psilocybe	Hemispherical to convex, often with a slight pimple at the centre; surface is slightly sticky or greasy due to a gelatinous pellicle; has white, cottony veil remnants at the margin when young; reddish-brown to orange-brown, fading to yellowish-brown when dry.	Grows on dung and manure-rich soils/ April	Small reddish-brown cap, smooth stem, non-hallucinogenic, inedible
8.	<i>Ganoderma applanatum</i> (Pers.) Pat. Ganodermataceae	Artist's conk	White underside that turns dark brown when scratched, a white-to-cinnamon interior, and a lack of a distinct stem; cap woody, fan-to-hoof-shaped, and usually sessile.	Found on dead or living hardwood trees/ April	Inedible
9.	<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i> (Curtis) P. Karst. Ganodermataceae	Reishi/ Lingzhi	Shiny, varnished, reddish-brown kidney-shaped cap; with a distinct, often lateral, stipe; stipe tawny to reddish-brown or black.	Grows on decaying hardwoods, especially oak and maple/ May	Edible (used medicinally, not for regular eating)

10.	<i>Inocybe catalaunica</i> Singer Inocybaceae	No widely known common name.	smooth-spored mushroom; non-marginate to slightly swollen stipe that is fully pruinose; Cap small to medium-sized, typically brownish, often smooth or slightly fibrillose, lacking a strong umbo.	Found in mixed woodlands, often under broadleaf trees/ May	Poisonous
11.	<i>Leucocoprinus cepistipes</i> (Sowerby) Pat. Agaricaceae	Onion-stalk parasol	Conical to bell-shaped, finely scaled (floccose) cap with a striate margin, turning white-buff to grey-brown with age, and a slender stem; fragile ring and a slightly club-shaped bulbous base.	Grows on decaying plant matter, compost, greenhouses/ April	Edible (but not commonly consumed)
12.	<i>Macrolepiota albuminosa</i> (Berk.) Pegler Agaricaceae	No widely known common name	Surface white, pale tan, or buff-brown, with brown spots/ scales that are denser near the centre. Gills free, crowded, and white in colour, turning pinkish or light brown with maturity; persistent ring with movable collar.	Forest floors and grassy areas with rich organic matter/ March	Edible.
13.	<i>Marasmius oreades</i> (Bolton) Fr. Marasmiaceae	Fairy ring mushroom	initially bell-shaped, becoming convex to broadly convex or flat, often with a slight central bump; cap is smooth, dry, and tan, buff, or pale cream-colored, which often turns lighter when dry; Gills white to pale tan.	Grows in grassy areas forming fairy rings/ April	Edible.

14.	<i>Parasola plicatilis</i> (Curtis) Psathyrellaceae	Fairy Inkcap or Trooping Crumble Cap	Small, paper-thin, deeply grooved plicate clip, greyish-brown, dark centre, fragile white stem.	Grows in dense clusters on decaying wood in moist, shaded areas/ February	It is not edible Used as Decomposer, Ecological Indicator.
15.	<i>Phallus indusiatus</i> (Vent. & Pers.) Phallaceae	Bamboo mushroom or long net stinkhorn.	Tall, white, spongy stalk (stipe) topped with a conical to bell-shaped, honeycombed cap.	Decaying wood and leaf litter in tropical forests/ March	Edible.
16.	<i>Pycnoporus sanguineus</i> (L.) Murrill Polyporaceae	Red Polypore	Bright, often zoned cap, a velvety to smooth texture and bright orange-red/ red-orange pores on the underside.	Dead hardwood in tropical and subtropical forests/ February	Inedible due to its tough texture.
17.	<i>Panaeolus</i> variant Bolbitiaceae	Bell cap mushroom	Small-to-medium, conical to convex, grey- brown-white caps, often with a mottled, grey- black gill appearance.	Nutrient-rich soils, dung, and grassy areas/ April	Edible.
18.	<i>Panaeolus antillarum</i> (Fr.) Dennis Bolbitiaceae	White dung mushroom	Smooth, shiny white to light grey, bell-shaped cap, black spore print, and long stipe; gills greyish when young, turning black and mottled as the spores mature.	Grows on dung and nutrient-rich soils in pastures/ April	Edible
19.	<i>Panaeolus semiovatus</i> (Sowerby) S. Lundell & Nannf. Bolbitiaceae	Common ink cap	Cap light tan/ buff to whitish; oval, conical or parabolic; sticky when wet and often wrinkles when dry; ring blackened by spores.	Nutrient-rich soils, often in grasslands, gardens, or wood chips/ May	Edible.

20.	<i>Skeletocutis nivea</i> (Jungh.) Jean Keller Polyporaceae	White crust fungus	Small, white, crust-like or bracket-like fruit bodies.	Found on dead hardwoods in tropical and temperate forests/ May	Inedible
21.	<i>Schizophyllum commune</i> Fr. Schizophyllaceae	Split gill	Small, sessile, shell-shaped caps with a white-to-greyish hairy surface; split-gilled hymenophore on the underside.	Found on decaying wood in forests and urban areas/ April	Edible
22.	<i>Stereum hirsutum</i> (Willd.) Pers. Stereaceae	Hairy curtain crust	Yellowish-orange, zonate, and densely hairy (hirsute) upper cap; semicircular, fan-shaped, or irregular with a leathery or tough texture; surface hairy with distinct concentric zones of colour.	Found on dead hardwood branches and logs/ May	Inedible
23.	<i>Trichaptum abietinum</i> (Pers. ex J.F. Gmel.) Ryvarden Polyporaceae	Violet-toothed polypore	Leathery, fan-shaped brackets that form crowded, overlapping clusters; cap leathery, tough, and flexible; surface hairy or velvety; flesh tough, pale brown to purplish brown.	Grows on dead conifer wood, especially fir and spruce/ May	Inedible
24.	<i>Trametes hirsute</i> (Wulfen) Lloyd Polyporaceae	Hairy bracket	Cap densely hairy, greyish-white, and concentrically zoned, semi-circular, fan-shaped, or kidney-shaped.	Found on dead hardwood logs and stumps/ May	Inedible
25.	<i>Trametes lactinea</i> (Berk.) Sacc. Polyporaceae	Lumpy bracket	Shelf-like, sessile; can be found growing in overlapping clusters or singly; upper surface of cap whitish to cream-colored or light yellow, often turning slightly brownish in age.	Found on dead hardwood logs and stumps/ May	Inedible

26.	<i>Trametes ochracea</i> (Pers.) Gilb. & Ryvarden Polyporaceae	Ochre bracket	Shelf-like, sessile white-rot fungus characterized by ochre-yellow to orange, finely hairy, and distinctively zoned caps. Creamy ochre pore layer; tough, thin flesh.	Found on dead hardwood trees and logs/ April	Inedible
27.	<i>Trametes versicolor</i> (L.) Lloyd Polyporaceae	Turkey tail	Thin, fan-shaped/ bracket-like caps with distinct, velvety, concentric, with grey, brown and black colours.	Dead or decaying hardwood logs and stumps/ March	Edible.
28.	<i>Volvariella volvacea</i> (Bull. ex Fr.) Singer Pluteaceae	Paddy straw mushroom	Distinct brownish-grey conical-to-convex cap (5–15 cm), free gills that turn pinkish-brown, a thick, persistent dark-coloured volva at the base, and the absence of a ring (annulus) on the stipe.	Grows on straw, compost, and organic waste in warm climates/ May	Edible (highly cultivated and nutritious)

Fig.2: Edible macrofungi: a. *Agaricus bisporus*, b. *Armillaria mellea*, c. *Coprinellus disseminates*, d. *Leucocoprinus cepistipes*, e. *Macrolepiota albuminosa*, f. *Marasmius oreades*, g. *Panaeolus antillarum*, h. *Panaeolus semiovatus*, i. *Panaeolus* variant, j. *Phallus indusiatus*, k. *Schizophyllum commune*, l. *Trametes versicolor*

Fig.3: Inedible macrofungi: a. *Amanita phalloides*, b. *Crepidotus mollis*, c. *Daldinia concentrica*, d. *Deconica coprophila*, e. *Ganoderma applanatum*, f. *Inocybe catalaunica*, g. *Parasola plicatilis*, h. *Skeletocutis nivea*, i. *Stereum hirsutum*, j. *Trametes hirsute*, k. *Trametes lactinea*, l. *Trametes ochracea*

Discussion

Macrofungi hold special importance in the present-day scenario of exploration and studies related to mycology. They have considerable nutritional value and contain compounds of medicinal importance [13]. Mushrooms are extensively consumed as they have low calorific value, serving as an important source of vitamins, essential minerals, proteins, fats and carbohydrates [1], [14]. Many macrofungal species produce secondary metabolites that can be toxic, mind-altering, antibiotic, antiviral, antibacterial [10], and anti-cancerous activity [11]. Mushrooms with psychoactive properties play a vital role in various native medicines. Some mushrooms are used in the treatment of diseases, dyeing wool and other natural fibres. Similar to yeasts and moulds, macrofungi also have immense biological and economic impact as they serve as food and medicine, biocontrol agents, and produce bioactive compounds such as anti-oxidants, anti-diabetic, hypocholesterolemic, anti-tumour, anti-cancer, immunomodulatory, anti-allergic, nephroprotective, and anti-microbial agents [12], [13]. Macrofungi are used in the bioremediation of industrial waste and the accumulation of heavy metals from the environment [6]. There are approximately 2166 worldwide recognized edible species, including approximately 470 species with medicinal properties [14]. Furthermore, macrofungi are useful indicators of health or age of an ecosystem [14].

Macrofungi exhibit great diversity in form, function, habitat, and ecological relationships. Their presence is often a sign of a healthy ecosystem, while their absence can indicate ecological imbalance. One of the most important aspects revealed during this study is the vast number of undescribed or poorly understood macrofungal species, particularly in biodiverse regions like the survey site chosen in this study. This shows the urgent need for more field research, documentation, and conservation efforts. Fungi are highly sensitive to environmental changes, habitat destruction and deforestation. Therefore, protecting fungal habitats is not only about preserving species, but also about safeguarding the intricate web of life that depends on them. Macrofungi also offer immense economic and medicinal value [12], [14]. Edible species are a vital part of local diets and global food industries, while medicinal fungi are used for modern and traditional therapies [14]. With ongoing scientific discoveries, the potential for new antibiotics, anticancer agents, and immunomodulatory compounds from macrofungi is becoming increasingly recognized [13].

Assam forms a major part of the Eastern Himalayan Biodiversity Region and is recognized as part of one of the two biodiversity hotspots in India. The state's climatic conditions have helped in the development of an exceptional diversity of ecological habitats, including forests, grasslands, and wetlands, which support a broad spectrum of plant and fungal life. Assam experiences a subtropical monsoon climate with an average annual rainfall of nearly 1,500 mm. Daytime temperatures during summers and the monsoons rise to around 35°C. Such environmental conditions favour the growth of a wide variety of macrofungal species [15]. Despite the considerable agro-industrial, medicinal

[16], and commercial potential of macrofungi, studies documenting the macrofungal diversity of Northeast India remain limited [17]. Various species of macrofungi are traditionally harvested from the wild and consumed by local tribes in Assam; however, due to the lack of reliable documentation and phytochemical investigations, little progress has been made toward their commercial cultivation. Scientific data on the characteristics of wild edible macrofungi are also insufficient, even as many of these species are gradually declining because of habitat loss. Therefore, systematic documentation of their diversity and distribution, along with detailed phytochemical studies, is urgently needed in Assam. The Sutargaon area of Assam supports a diverse macrofungal community. Although published information on the macrofungal diversity of this area is scarce, investigations from nearby localities and across Assam as a whole indicate the presence of a rich and varied macrofungal assemblage. In the present study, the diversity and distribution of macrofungi in the Sutargaon area of Guwahati, Assam, were examined.

A total of 28 macrofungal species were collected during the course of this investigation, representing the macrofungal diversity of the Sutargaon area of Guwahati, Assam. These taxa belong to 22 genera, all of which fall under the division Basidiomycota. The study of macrofungal diversity provides valuable insight into the often-overlooked yet indispensable components of terrestrial ecosystems. The findings of this work clearly demonstrate that macrofungi are not merely inhabitants of the forest floor or sources of food, but rather essential organisms with multifaceted roles in sustaining ecological equilibrium, promoting biodiversity, and supporting human welfare.

Conclusion

Macrofungi play a vital role in sustaining life on Earth. Although their remarkable diversity is frequently underestimated, it is crucial for maintaining ecosystem balance, promoting sustainable development, and offering promising opportunities for biomedical advancements. The outcomes of this study highlight the importance of ongoing research, systematic documentation, and effective conservation of fungal species. Encouraging increased awareness and deeper scientific exploration of macrofungi will enhance our understanding and appreciation of the intricate, remarkable, and essential fungal world that thrives beneath our feet.

Declaration

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

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